

Socio-Demographic Characteristics Associated with Substance Use and Abuse Among Students of Selected Secondary Schools in Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State

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Abstract:

This study investigated Socio-demographic characteristics associated with substance use and abuse among Students of selected Secondary Schools in Ado-Ekiti, South/West, Nigeria. This descriptive cross-sectional survey utilized purposive sampling technique to select 327 final year Senior Secondary School (SSS) students randomly chosen from three (3) selected Secondary Schools in Ado Local Government Area (LGA) of Ekiti State, Southwest, Nigeria. Data was collected using a pre-tested, specially designed and self-administered questionnaire and analysis was done with Statistical Package for Social sciences (SPSS) version 20. Descriptive statistics and Inferential statistics were used to analyse data at 0.05% level of significance. The age group of 16-20 years (93.6%) were the main respondents in this study, 145 (44.3%) were males, 182 (55.7%) were females; respondents from polygamous homes reported higher (47.6%) percentage of substance use, also respondents from broken homes show higher affinity for psychoactive substance use. The main source of psychoactive substance use/initiation among secondary school students were through friends/peers 120 (36.7%) and through media 99 (30.3%). Most prominent among reasons advanced for psychoactive

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substance consumption were to keep awake to study late into the night 141 (43.1%) and to improve performance ((41.9%). This study finds that socio-demographic characteristics impacts some influence on predisposing factors culminating to substance use and abuse ($\chi^2=11.138$, $p=0.001$). Appropriate preventive measures should be put in place to curtail this socio-medical menace.

Keywords: Socio-Demographic Characteristics, Substance Use and Abuse, Students,

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Introduction

Substance use and abuse seems to have risen worldwide and in Nigeria even among teenagers and secondary school students. In today's society, it is common to see people swallow, smoke, inject and sniff different substances into their bodies so as to achieve some purpose. Onyencho, et al (2018) stated that the use of psychoactive substances is increasingly becoming a custom in our society today. Psychoactive substance refers to natural or man-made products which change bodily functions physically and mentally when used. Such substances influence reasoning, feelings and behaviour especially when taken in surplus.

According to World Health Organisation (WHO, 2016), substance abuse refers to the unsafe or hazardous use of substances including alcohol and illicit drugs. Also, Griffin (1990) described substance abuse as the surplus use of a substance (including drugs) in a way that is injurious to self, society or both. This includes physical and psychological dependence. National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC, 2018) expands that the term substance abuse refers to excessive and continuous use of a substance without respect for the medically or culturally accepted systems. It could also be viewed as the use of substance(s) to the level that it disturbs the well-being and social functioning of an individual. As such, substance abuse may be defined as the irresponsible, illicit over dependence or misuse of substance(s) with or without prior medical diagnosis from qualified health practitioners.

It could be concluded from above definitions that 'substances' include alcohol and other drugs (legal or illegal) as well as some other edible products. In simpler terms, substances are not restricted to manufactured drugs but include such other substances such as alcohol and tobacco. In the context of this study, substance use is the consumption of medicines or substances that have been prescribed or recommended by a competent health professional. On the other hand, substance abuse is the consumption of non-prescribed medicine by individuals.

There is also broadcasting reports day-in, day-out of increasing use of psychoactive substances with resulting antisocial activities among youths. For example, cases of insecurity in Nigeria such as kidnapping, cyber-crime, violent demonstrations, thuggery, incessant armed robbery, arson, religious upheavals, cultism, and prostitution among teenagers and youths in Nigeria could be associated with psychoactive substance use and abuse (Punch Newspaper 2019, Jan., 15;). Moreover, Isaac, et al., (2018), explained that societal problems of lower life expectancy, mental problems, unplanned pregnancy, accidents, incidence of sexual aggression and other offenses are some of the consequences of substance use and abuse.

These days one hears so much about young people getting addicted to alcohol and illicit drugs. Newspapers, radio and television programmers feature the challenge of substance abuse in great detail. Health authorities warn the public about this danger. There is increasing drift of alcohol craving and other drug abuse issues (Idowu, et al., 2018). The use of psychoactive substances such as tobacco, alcohol and other drugs has been exposed to play a key role in adolescent illnesses and death. When under influence of psychoactive substance(s), teenagers are at increased risk for injuries, interpersonal violence, unprotected sex, human immune deficiency virus (HIV) infection, and other sexually transmitted

infections. Psychoactive substance abuse is a major factor in teenager's deaths, kidnapping, cultism, automobile accidents, manslaughters, and suicides.

Most of previous studies on substance abuse focused on prevalence, pattern of use, type and perceived effects. The area of socio-demographic attributes associated with the use and abuse of substances has not been researched into at secondary school level. However, result of a study conducted among university students in Iran shows that mother's educational qualifications, place of residence, economic status, and parents' divorce was the most influential predictive factors in substance abuse (Jalilian, et al., 2015). Similarly, Onyencho et al (2018) revealed that males constituted the significant majority of substance abusers (85.7%), a large percentage were never married, half of them unemployed, and most of them had less than secondary education.

The researcher noticed that the challenge of substance abuse is present among secondary school students and impacting the lives of teenage students and youths. For example, sometimes in October, 2019; it was in the newsprint that a male student of Olaoluwa Muslim Grammar school, Ado-Ekiti collapsed after overdose of Indian hemp consumption, which was reported to have occurred during cult initiation in a bush around the school premises. Students have been involved in drugs and illicit activities around the school recently. Also, Ado Grammar School, Ado-Ekiti was in the newsprint late 2018 with reports of violent attacks among her students. Again, All Souls' Anglican grammar school was also in the news sometimes in May 2012, that a 19-member gang of teenage cultist was unmasked at the school. Also, two male teachers of the school were sacked for proven sexual molestation of female students of the school on 2nd March, 2020. In addition, it is a common knowledge that a number of teenage vagrant psychotics wandering the streets, parks and neighbourhood have risen extremely in our society and this trend seem to have been connected to psychoactive substance ingestion/injection.

Similarly, media reports - the Punch newspaper publication of 15th January, 2019; reported that the deputy governor of Ekiti-State, Bisi Egbeyemi lamented on the high consumption of hard drugs, including Indian hemp, in some parts of Ekiti State, including Ado-Ekiti, the state capital. Egbeyemi named some of the areas in Ado-Ekiti as Atikankan, Oke Ila, Odo-Ado, Idemo and Iworoko road. A lot of studies in Nigeria have examined prevalence and type of substance abuse among students, as well as the perceived effects, but not many have conducted a study that linked socio-demographic variables to substance use and abuse among secondary school students in Nigeria and especially South west, Nigeria.

Due to the reported rising trend of substance use and abuse amongst teenagers and youths in Ekiti State and the effects on our society; this study sampled some teenage students from three senior secondary schools in Ado-Ekiti, Southwest, Nigeria, to investigate certain socio-demographic characteristics associated with substance abuse. It has been demonstrated that teenagers have been involved in risky behaviour such as substance abuse, hence senior secondary school has huge number of youths aged 11-19 years

This study specifically:

1. examined if respondents abuse psychoactive substance(s);
2. examined predisposing factors of substance use among teenage respondents; and
3. determine reasons for students' use and abuse of substance(s)

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised for this study:

1. Do respondents abuse psychoactive substance(s)?
2. What are the predisposing factors of substance abuse among teenage secondary school respondents?
3. What are the reasons for students' use and abuse of psychoactive substance(s)?

Research Hypothesis

1. Gender, family type, parents' marital status and socio-economic status of parents have no significant influence on predisposing factors of substance use/abuse among students of secondary schools.

Methodology

The study design adapted in this study is a quantitative descriptive cross-sectional survey. The study was conducted in Ado-Ekiti, the capital city of Ekiti state in Southwestern, Nigeria and situated 92 miles (148 km) east of Ibadan. The study population comprised 1544 senior secondary students from three selected schools in Ado-Ekiti, South-West, Nigeria. The total sample size for the study was 327, calculated using the formula for simple proportion as suggested by Krejcie and Morgan (1970) to determine sample size for research computations. A multistage sampling technique was used in the selection of study participants.

The instrument used in gathering of data was a facilitated self-administered questionnaire developed by the researcher reviewing previous studies. Questionnaire was developed in four parts to obtain data on the relevant variables of the study such as: socio-demographic characteristics, substance use, predisposing factors, and reasons for substance abuse. To ensure that the research instrument captures pertinent variables of the study, the questionnaire was validated through content validity and face validity by experts in the field of Nursing. The internal consistency and stability of the research instrument to produce equally alike results over several administrations was determined using the test re-test technique. The test re-test study utilized 10% of the study population (36); total sampling population is 360. The questionnaire was administered twice to respondents chosen randomly from 3 non-selected schools for this study, and at separate intervals. The responses from both administrations were subjected to the Pearson's Product Moment Correlation and the scores were: 0.922 for Sources of information/Initiators of psychoactive substance abuse; 0.983 for predisposing factors adduced to substance use and abuse; and 0.893 for the Reasons for Psychoactive Substance use. All exceeded the benchmark score of 0.70 thus, the instrument used for data collection was considered reliable.

The questionnaire was administered by the researcher to the students in their various schools. Brief explanations were given with details of how the students were expected to answer the questionnaire. The Questionnaire was given only to respondents who satisfy the inclusion criteria and collected on the spot. They were encouraged to ask questions on areas they needed clarification, and explanations were provided as needed. The method of data analysis for this study was descriptive and inferential statistics.

Results**Demographic Characteristics****Table 1: Gender characteristics of respondents**

Gender	Schools			Total
	All Souls' Anglican G.S.	Ado Grammar School	Olaoluwa Muslim G.S.	
Male	46 (14.1%)	65 (19.9%)	34 (10.4%)	145 (44.3%)
Female	74 (22.6%)	44 (13.5%)	64 (19.6%)	182 (55.7%)
Total	120 (36.7%)	109 (33.3%)	98 (30%)	327 (100%)

Table 1 shows that majority 120 (36.7%) of the study sample was chosen from All Souls' Anglican Grammar school, 109 (33.3%) respondents from Ado Grammar school and 98 (30%) respondents from Olaoluwa Muslim Grammar school. The gender distribution of the respondents showed that 145 male respondents (44.3%) and 182 females (55.7%) respondents were sampled in all the three selected schools. While Ado Grammar School has the highest number 65 (19.9%) of male participants All Souls' Anglican Grammar School has the highest number 74 (22.6%) of female participants.

Table 2: Family Type characteristics of respondents

Family type or background	Schools			Total
	All Souls' Anglican G.S.	Ado Grammar School	Olaoluwa Muslim G.S.	
Monogamy	77 (34.7%)	83 (37.4%)	62 (27.9%)	222 (67.9%)
Polygamy	43 (41.0%)	26 (24.8%)	36 (34.3%)	105 (32.1%)
Total	120 (36.7%)	109 (33.3%)	98 (30.0%)	327 (100%)

From table 2, majority of respondents 222 (67.9%) are from monogamous homes while 105 respondents (32.1%) are from polygamous background. All Souls' Anglican Grammar school has the highest number (43; 41%) of students from polygamous homes, Ado Grammar school has highest proportion (83; 37.4%) of respondents from monogamous family.

Table 3: Marital Status and Socioeconomic status of respondents' parents

Marital status of parents	All Souls' Anglican G.S.	Ado Grammar School	Olaoluwa Muslim G.	Total
Still married	98 (35.8%)	93 (33.9%)	83 (30.3%)	274 (83.3%)
Divorced	4 (33.3%)	5 (41.7%)	3 (25.0%)	12 (3.7%)
Separated	18 (43.9%)	11 (26.8%)	12 (29.3%)	41 (12.5%)
Total	120 (36.7%)	109 (33.3%)	98 (30.0%)	327 (100%)
Socio-economic Status of Parents				
High income (N600,000 and above)	40 (37.7%)	35 (33%)	31 (29.2%)	106 (32.4%)

Middle (Below N400,000)	61 (32.8%)	67 (36%)	58 (31.2%)	186 (56.9%)
Low income (Below N50,000)	19 (54.3%)	7 (20%)	9 (25.7%)	35 (10.7%)
Total	120 (36.7%)	109 (33.3%)	98 (30%)	327 (100%)

From table 3, Ado Grammar School has the highest number (5; 41.7%) of respondents from divorced parents, All Souls' Anglican Grammar School has greatest proportion (18; 43.9%) of students from separated parents. In all schools combined, majority of the respondents, 274 (83.8%) have parents who are still married, 41 (12.5%) separated, while 12 respondents (3.7%) are from divorced parents. The socio-economic status of the parents as distributed show that 186 (56.9%) are in the middle and 106 respondents (32.4%) from the high-income group.

Question 1: Do respondents abuse psychoactive substance(s)?

	Ado Grammar School	All Souls' Anglican G.S.	Olaoluwa Muslim G.	Total
Ever Used psychoactive substance				
Substance User	26 (27.4%)	38 (40.0%)	31 (32.6%)	95 (29.1%)
Non substance user	83 (35.8%)	82 (35.3%)	67 (28.9%)	232 (70.9%)
Total	109 (33.3%)	120 (36.7%)	98 (30%)	327 (100%)
One or both Parents Use Psychoactive substance				
Parent substance user	10 (16.1%)	25 (40.3%)	27 (43.5%)	62 (19%)
Non substance user	99 (37.4%)	95 (35.8%)	71 (26.8%)	265 (81%)
Total	109 (33.3%)	120 (36.7%)	98 (30%)	327 (100%)
Respondent Still Use Psychoactive substance				
Current User of Substance	33 (28.7%)	46 (40%)	36 (31.3%)	115 (35.2%)
Non-User of substance	76 (35.8%)	74 (34.9%)	62 (29.2%)	212 (64.8%)
Total	109 (33.3%)	120 (36.7%)	98 (30%)	327 (100%)

Table 4: Substance use among respondents by Schools

Source: Field Survey, 2020. Compiled Using SPSS 20

The study considered the abuse of substance(s) by student respondents, and respondents' parents. Table 4 shows the response pattern. A little under third 95 (29.1%) of the respondents have ever used substances at one time in their life; while 62 (19%) of the respondents have parents, who use substance(s). Some 115 respondents (35.2%) still use substance/s. Breakdown shows that All Souls' Anglican Grammar School has the highest proportion (40%) of current substance user followed by Olaoluwa Muslim Grammar school with 31.3% and Ado Grammar school has the least (28.7%) proportion of student current substance user. Furthermore, it could be inferred that respondents from Olaoluwa Muslim Grammar school has highest proportion (43.5%) of parents who use substance.

Question 2: What are the predisposing factors of substance abuse among teenage secondary school respondents?

Table 5: Respondents view on Influence of Predisposing factors on Substance abuse
Source: Field Survey, 2020. Compiled Using SPSS 20

Variables	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Adolescents' curiosity/ inquisitiveness can influence psychoactive substance use?		
Influenced	138	42.2
Not Influenced	189	57.8
Experimentation with psychoactive substance like friends do		
Influenced	111	33.9
Not Influenced	216	66.1
Advertisement of psychoactive substance may influence substance use/abuse		
Influenced	147	45.0
Not Influenced	180	55.0
Easy Availability of psychoactive substance can influence its use		
Influenced	126	38.5
Not Influenced	201	61.5
Parental Deprivation might influence psychoactive substance use?		
Influenced	107	32.7
Not Influenced	220	67.3
Open/Street Use may influence psychoactive substance use		
Influenced	134	41.0
Not Influenced	193	59.0

This study featured six community-level factors that may predispose the use and abuse of substance/s such as, curiosity, experimentation with friends, media portrayal through advertisement and jingles; availability of substance for purchase, parental deprivation due to death, divorce, separation and discord, as well as the open/street use of psychoactive substance in outdoor situations. Table 4.9 depicts the respondent's responses.

From Table 5 the common reasons for substance use/abuse were for medical reasons (45.9%), to stay awake and read at night (43.1%), to improve performance ((41.9%), to enhance relaxation and sleep (39.4%), to feel excited and happy (euphoria, 39.1%) among others.

Question 3: What are the reasons for students' use and abuse of psychoactive substance(s)?

Table 5 Respondents' reasons for substance use/abuse

S/N	Variables	Frequency	Percentages (%)
1.	Medical reasons/as recommended by doctor	150	45.9
2.	To feel Excited and Happy	128	39.1
3.	For Relaxation and Sleep	129	39.4

4.	Boldness and avoid shyness	121	37.0
5.	To overcome nervousness	114	34.9
6.	To increase mental alertness	123	37.6
7.	To improve performance	137	41.9
8.	To stimulate me into action	127	38.8
9.	To gain acceptance of my friends (peer groups)	118	36.1
10.	To emulate my close family	116	35.5
11.	To stay awake to read at night	141	43.1

Source: Field Survey, 2020. Compiled Using SPSS 20

From Table 5 the common reasons for substance use/abuse were for medical reasons (45.9%), to stay awake and read at night (43.1%), to improve performance ((41.9%), to enhance relaxation and sleep (39.4%), to feel excited and happy (euphoria, 39.1%). Other reasons given for psychoactive substance use by respondents include to stimulate into action (38.8%), enhance mental alertness (37.6%), gain acceptance of my friends/peer groups (36.1%), emulate close family that indulges in psychoactive substance use and abuse (35.5%) and lastly to overcome nervousness (34.9%).

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: Gender, family type, parents' marital status and socio-economic status of parents have no significant influence on predisposing factors of substance use/abuse among students of secondary schools.

Table 6: Gender, Parents' Marital status, Family type, Socioeconomic status of parents and predisposing factors of substance use/abuse among students of secondary schools

Variable	Influenced (%)	Not influence d (%)	Total (%) n=327	χ^2	p-value	Crame r's V
Gender * Curiosity about psychoactive substance/s use				11.13 8 ^a	0.001	.185
Male	76 (52.4%)	69 (47.6%)	145 (100%)			
Female	62 (34.1%)	120 (65.9%)	182 (100%)			
Marital status of parents * Advertisement				9.580 a	0.008	.171
Still married	122 (44.5%)	152 (55.5%)	274 (100%)			
Divorced	1 (8.3%)	11 (91.7%)	12 (100%)			
Separated	24 (58.5%)	17 (41.5%)	41(100%)			
Family type or background * Easy Availability				5.392	0.020	.128
Monogamy	76 (34.2%)	146 (65.8%)	222 (100%)			

Polygamy	50 (47.6%)	55 (52.4%)	105 (100%)	a		
Family type or background * Experimentation with psychoactive substance like friends						
Monogamy	67 (30.2%)	155 (69.8%)	222 (100%)	4.370	0.037	.116
Polygamy	44 (41.9%)	61 (58.1%)	105 (100%)	a		
Socioeconomic Status of Parent * Experimentation with psychoactive substance						
High (N600,000 & above)	46 (43.4%)	60 (56.6%)	106(100%)	6.324	0.042	.139
Middle (below N400,000)	54 (29%)	132(71%)	186(100%)	a		
Low (below N50,000)	11 (31.4%)	24 (68.6%)	35 (100%)			

Source: Field Survey, 2020. Compiled Using SPSS 20

Table 6 shows the Chi-square of Gender, Parents' Marital status, Family type, Socio-economic status variables and their relationship to predisposing factors of substance use/abuse among secondary school students, all at 5% level of significance. It was shown that Socio-demographic characteristics (gender, parents' marital status, family type, parents' socio-economic status) were most significantly associated with predisposing factors of substance use and abuse, where gender ($\chi^2=11.138$, $p=0.001$) was associated to curiosity about psychoactive substance use.

Also, parents' marital status ($\chi^2=9.580$, $p=0.008$) had significant relationship to media advertisement of psychoactive substance/s on radio and television shows. Family type/background was found to have significant relationship to substance/s been easily available to buy ($\chi^2=5.392$, $p=0.020$) and also has significant relationship to experimentation ($\chi^2=4.370$, $p=0.037$) with psychoactive substance/s. Furthermore, socio-economic status of parents ($\chi^2=6.324$, 0.042) has significant relationship to experimentation with substances.

Discussion of Findings

A general use rate of 29.1% and current user rate of 35.2% was reported in this study, out of which 19% of the respondents had parents who are substance users. The current substance use rate of 35.2% in this study was consistent with the studies of Duru, et. al, (2017) who reported 45.3% current use of psychoactive substance. However, this was much lower than 69.25 reported by Onyencho, et al (2018); and 78% was reported by Isaac et al (2018). However, it is higher than 23.7% reported by Tawasu (2005) in Maiduguri. These differences could be a result of difference in methodologies adopted as well as difference in study population. Also, age difference of secondary school students compared to tertiary institution student could equally be a factor. Another factor that could account for different values include factors such as, socio-cultural characteristics of respondents.

Previous studies also found significant association between substance use and religiosity with those with high level of involvement in religiosity been less likely to use psychoactive substance (Abdurahman et al, 2019; Manyike, et al, 2016).

No single reason can be attributed to the use and abuse of psychoactive substance/s. In this study, reasons given for psychoactive substance consumption include diverse factors such as, Keeping awake to study at night especially during assessment test/assignments; to gain acceptance of friends and peers; emulate close family substance abuser; improve performance; medical reasons; relaxation and sleep; excitement and happiness (euphoria); stimulate to action; To increase mental alertness; for boldness and avoid shyness; and also to overcome nervousness.

These were all similar to findings reported in previous studies such as Duru, et. al (2017; Abayomi, et al., 2012; Adekeye, et al 2011; Oshodi, et. al, 2010). Also, Barati et al (2012) reported high rate of caffeine use among students to keep awake to read at night especially during test assignments.

The outcome of the research hypothesis revealed that variability in predisposing factors of substance use/abuse is accounted for by socio-demographic characteristic as shown in table 6. These include gender, family type/background, marital status of parents, mother's and guardian educational level, Parents socioeconomic status, as well as the level of religious involvement. Chi-square reported significant influence of aforementioned socio-demographic variables on predisposing factors of substance use/abuse with $p < 0.05$ at 5% level of significance. The predisposing factors referred include: curiosity about substance, Experimentation with psychoactive substance, advertisement of substance, easy availability of psychoactive substance, parental deprivation due to death, divorce, and separation, as well as the open street use of substance. This study revealed that advertisement (45%), open street use (41%), as well as curiosity (42.2%) were the commonest push factor for use of psychoactive substance/s. Igwe and Ojinnaka (2010) reported similar result in a study at Kaduna where experimentation was the commonest tempting factor for substance use.

Conclusion

Psychoactive substance use/abuse among secondary school students is high with 38.3% substance use reported in one of the schools. The main source of psychoactive substance use initiation among secondary school students were through friends/peers and through media portrayal. Most prominent among reasons advanced for psychoactive substance consumption were to keep awake to study late into the night as well as peer group pressure amongst others. Findings also show that Socio-demographic characteristics impacts some influence on predisposing factors culminating to substance use and abuse.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that

- i. Psychoactive substance awareness and education campaigns targeted at teenagers and secondary school students are imperative. Such health education and sensitization programs on the effect of substance abuse for teenager and families through health care facilities, school curriculum, religious and worship centres should be promoted. This could take the form of rallies, talk shows, and film shows that depicts negative outcome of psychoactive substance consumption. Positive perception about

- psychoactive substance use held by teenage students can be countered thereby reducing tendency for substance abuse.
- ii. There is need for widespread schools' recognition of substance use/abuse problem among students by Inspectorate units of both State and Federal Ministry of Education as well as Education Department of Local Government Authority. There should be a deliberate effort aimed towards curbing this malady beyond just having a written drug policy on the part of schools.
 - iii. Routine and regular checks of students' bags and belongings should be carried out by school teachers.
 - iv. Advertisement of alcoholic drinks, cigarettes, tobacco and other forms of psychoactive substances using celebrities often seen as role models to the younger ones should be discouraged.

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